

Terpenoids: Part LIV. A Synthesis of Sesquicarene

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As part of our investigations¹⁻³ towards the syntheses of cyclopropenoids through copper catalysed intramolecular cyclization of properly substituted olefinic α -diazoketones^{4,5}, we wish to report a synthesis of sesquicarene, a sesquiterpene hydrocarbon with structure⁶ (I), isolated from the essential oil of fruits of *Schisandra chinensis* Bull.

The scheme illustrates the sequence of the reactions employed :—

The aldehyde (II) obtained by deketalization of ethyl 5,5-ethylenedioxy-2-methylbutanoate⁷ was treated with isopropenyl magnesium bromide in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran to form ethyl 2,6-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-heptenoate (III). The carbinol (III) was converted into its vinyl ether (IV) with ethyl vinyl ether⁸ under gentle reflux in the presence

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of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate as catalyst which on Claisen rearrangement⁹ in a sealed tube under nitrogen atmosphere yielded ethyl 2, 6-dimethyl-8-formyl-5-octenoate (V) (b.p. 110°/10 mm, yield 60%). This aldehyde gave yellow dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative (m.p. 135–36°).

The aldehyde (V) when submitted to Wittig reaction¹⁰ with triphenylisopropylphosphonium iodide in dimethylsulphoxide afforded (VI) in 65% yield (b.p. 112–15°/10 mm.). The ester (VI) was hydrolysed with aqueous alkali to give the corresponding acid (VII) which was converted into its chloride (VIII) with thionyl chloride in benzene. The acid chloride (VIII) on reaction with ethereal solution of diazomethane under usual conditions^{4,5} formed α -diazoketone (IX) which was refluxed with catalytic amount of anhydrous copper sulphate^{1–5} in cyclohexane to produce the bicyclic ketone (X) in 10% overall yield from the acid (VIII). The ketone (X) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to give the alcohol (XI) which on dehydration with phosphorus oxychloride in pyridine furnished sesquicarene (I). The synthetic hydrocarbon (I) was characterised by comparing its I.R. spectrum with that of naturally occurring sesquicarene⁶.

Most of the compounds were purified by chromatography and fractional distillation under reduced pressure. The intermediates showed their characteristic I.R. spectra and gave satisfactory analytic data, wherever necessary. Full details of the work will be communicated in due course when more data (n.m.r.) is available.

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